

Spin 1/2 and Matrices

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The Dirac equation follows from the linearization of Einstein's momentum-energy equation and leads to 4x4 matrices which contain the 2x2 Pauli matrices. The four vector free particle solution contains two spinor solutions, with the second containing p and E terms which convert the equation linear in E and p back into the quadratic momentum energy equation.

In this note, we consider momentum p in the z direction and use the momentum energy relation without any quantum derivatives. In such a case, a two vector appears as one makes the equation linear with the second component containing E and p terms needed to make the equation quadratic again. A four vector is not needed, in other words there is no spin. It only becomes necessary if one considers p as having px,py,pz values. In such a case, one must obtain $p^2 = p_x^2 + p_y^2 + p_z^2$ (in the momentum energy equation) and this requires matrices which act as an orthogonal basis i.e. the Pauli matrices if one wishes to use non-vectors throughout. (Here a matrix is being called a non-vector.) In this general situation, the two vector becomes a four vector with the Pauli matrices representing a kind of rotation of the spinor coordinates even though px, py and pz represent linear motion. We argue that one may have degenerate motion of the charge in the electron i.e. the turning motion (constrained motion) of the Pauli matrices linked to px, py and pz lead to charge motion which is degenerate with respect to the energy-momentum equation, but is discerned by a magnetic field.

Simplified Approach

Consider the energy-momentum equation with $p=p_z$, i.e there are simply numbers mo, E and pz:

$$E^2 = m^2 c^4 + p^2 c^2 \quad ((1))$$

A simple way to linearize this is to consider:

$$(E - mc^2) = p_z c / (E + mc^2) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) would be linear if not for the factor $p_z / (E + mc^2)$, but one may extend it to two dimensions and place $p_z / (E + mc^2)$ in the second dimension by using matrices:

$$\begin{pmatrix} E & | & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & | & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} | & A \\ | & B \end{pmatrix} - mc^2 \begin{pmatrix} | & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & | & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} | & A \\ | & B \end{pmatrix} = p_z \begin{pmatrix} | & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & | & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} | & A \\ | & B \end{pmatrix} \quad ((3))$$

This yields: $(E - mc^2) A = p_z B$ so $B = A p_z / (E - mc^2)$ and $(E + mc^2) B = p_z A$ which also yields $B = p_z / (E + mc^2) A$.

No Pauli matrices or spinors appear in this solution, but there are two solutions A and B just as in the Dirac case (except in that case each solution is a spinor). In order to obtain A and B as spinors it seems that one must consider three components p_x, p_y and p_z .

Reason for Linearization

One may ask why one should linearize the energy-momentum equation ((1)). One might argue that originally de Broglie suggested that an electron had a wavelength like a photon and try to compare the two. From Maxwell's classical electromagnetic equations, one may form a wave equation for E and B (electric and magnetic fields). There exist, however, linear equations:

$$dB/dt = -\text{grad} \times E \text{ and } dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B \quad ((4))$$

E and B, however, are not momentum and energy. Furthermore, the fact that both a photon and an electron have a wavelength does not mean that they are identical in all ways. An electron has spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and a charge. A photon has spin 1 and seems to be governed by the E (electric field) and B (magnetic field) which are perpendicular to each other and the momentum vector and of the same magnitude. An electron has an electric field and a small magnetic field if velocity is low. It does, however, have a physical charge which, if it could move, could create a current as an intrinsic property even if $v \rightarrow 0$.

An alternative approach is to consider the free particle relativistic action with v (velocity) written as x/t :

$$\text{Action} = \int (-m_0) \sqrt{1 - x^2/t^2} \quad ((5))$$

We have shown in previous notes that $d\text{Action}/dt = -E$ and $d\text{Action}/dx = p$ ((6))

In special relativity x and ct are part of a four vector, but the action, which governs classical motion, is not symmetric in these two components of 4 space. x is in the numerator and t in the denominator in v and there is an extra t from $\int dt$.

Nevertheless, if one wishes to treat x and t on the same footing and hence d/dt and d/dx on the same footing, one might consider an equation linear in $d\text{Action}/dt$ and $d\text{Action}/dx$, $d\text{Action}/dy$, $d\text{Action}/dz$. This equation, however, must be consistent with $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$.

In ((3)), it is shown that one needs to create a two vector to have the appearance of a linear equation with p and E pieces in the second component. For $p=p_z$, one has $|A, B|$ but A and B are scalars, not spinors as in the Dirac (or Pauli case).

The spinor behaviour appears when one considers p_x, p_y, p_z i.e. three directions in space. In such a case, one must move from a linear number/matrix expression with p_x, p_y, p_z and matrices to $p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$ which appears in the energy-momentum equation. One uses a scalar equation with p_x, p_y and p_z as numbers and so one needs matrices to play the role of orthogonal basis vectors (in an overall sense) i.e. instead of taking the dot product of two

vectors one considers a scalar matrix sum and takes the scalar product of two such objects to obtain the same result.

This leads to:

$$Q = S_x p_x + S_y p_y + S_z p_z \quad \text{such that } Q^2 = p_x^2 + p_y^2 + p_z^2 \quad ((7))$$

In particular, $S_j S_k = \delta_{j,k} I + i \epsilon_{jkl} S_l$ from (1). (I is an identity matrix.) Then:

$p_j S_j p_k S_k = p_j p_j + i p_j p_k \epsilon_{jkl} S_l$ (sum on repeated indices) but $p_j p_k$ is symmetric in j,k and ϵ_{ijk} antisymmetric so the result is $p_j p_j$ (sum on j). Thus the Pauli matrices are not exactly like basis vectors in three-space, but their overall effect in a product of Q with Q is the same as if basis vectors had been used.

A similar treatment could be applied to a right angle triangle to obtain the Pythagoras relation. It is through ((7)) that the 2x2 Pauli matrices and the idea of spinors emerge it seems. From the momentum energy relation point of view the Pauli matrices which represent a kind of constrained motion have no effect on energy based on motion through space. An electron, however, has charge and this degenerate constrained motion may be linked to charge motion in three-space. A two x two matrix is the smallest matrix which may satisfy ((7)). A scalar does not. Thus, one has the unusual situation that a two matrix is linked to a kind of constrained motion.

((7)) changes ((3)), but not by much. One need only have 1 in the matrices become the 2x2 identity matrix and p_z become:

$$S_x p_x + S_y p_y + S_z p_z \quad ((8)) \quad \text{For } p_x=p_y=0 \text{ one has } S_z p_z \text{ where } S_z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

This is more complicated than ((3)) and shows that even in the p_z case there is a kind of constrained charge motion which does not appear unless one is thinking of matrices which act as the basis vectors of 3-space and are linked to rotations (of the charge it seems).

One may ask why this approach does not also apply to a photon. For example, consider:

$$E I = p_x S_x + p_y S_y + p_z S_z \quad ((8)) \quad \text{where } I \text{ is the } 2 \times 2 \text{ identity matrix}$$

Multiplying each side by itself yields $EE = p_x^2 + p_y^2 + p_z^2$. It has been argued above that a photon is governed by equations involving E (electric field) and B. In fact, a photon quantum equation may be obtained using $E + iB$ as the vector wavefunction and ϵ_{ijk} (the Levi Civita symbol) as the spin matrices where i represents the ith spin matrix and jk the entries. It seems the physics of the photon is based on the fields E and B and not on any charge moving in various directions. Thus, ((8)) is a math equation which does not correspond to any physical phenomenon. For the electron there is charge and so it is possible to have it be linked to motion represented by the Pauli matrices.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that Einstein's energy momentum equation ((1)) is quadratic in E , p and m_0 . This is reminiscent of a right angle triangle Pythagoras equation. One cannot simply add side lengths because there is a rotation of 90 degrees associated with one side. One may argue that a similar phenomenon occurs for the energy-momentum equation. This rotation is linked to the axes of p_x, p_y, p_z . In fact, one may choose the z axis parallel to p and only have p_z . Physically, however, the rotational effect of coordinates for p_x, p_y, p_z may be linked to constrained (rotational) motion of charges. Instead of using vectors and dot products, one may use scalar quantities which requires the use of matrices (as "numbers" behaving like basis vectors). The smallest such matrix is 2×2 and leads to the Pauli matrices. One may linearize $E^2 = p_x^2 + p_y^2 + p_z^2 + m_0^2$ to see the various "rotations" (Pauli matrix operations). Linearizing means one must first consider a two vector solution (A, B) with $B = p_z / (E + m_0)$ for $p = p_z$. With a full p_x, p_y, p_z , p_z becomes $p_x s_x + p_y s_y + p_z s_z$ where s_i are the Pauli matrices. In such a case, A and B become spinors i.e. 2 vectors. This suggests internal motion related to the p_x, p_y, p_z orthogonal orientations in space. This internal (constrained hence perhaps rotational motion) may possibly apply to the charge of an electron. A photon has no charge and so the above analysis with $m_0 = 0$ would not apply. Instead, a photon is physically associated with its E (electric) and B (magnetic fields) which are perpendicular to each other and to the direction of motion and of the same magnitude.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pauli_matrices